

Formation Constants of Bipositive Metal Ion-Bipyridine-1-Hydroxy-2-Naphthoic Acid or 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthoic Acid Complexes in Solution

PRADYOT KUMAR DATTA

Chemical Laboratories, D.H.S.K. College, Dibrugarh-786 001

and

MADHUP CHANDRA and ARUN K. DEY*

Chemical Laboratories, University of Allahabad,
Allahabad-211 002

Manuscript received 2 January 1979, revised 5 May 1980,
accepted 9 July 1980

THE present communication describes pH-metric studies^{1,2} on ternary complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) ions with 2,2-bipyridine (bipy) as a primary and 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid (1,2 HNA) or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthoic acid (2,1 HNA) as a secondary ligand (L) in 50% v/v aqueous-ethanol medium at 25° and at an ionic strength 0.1 (KNO₃). The evaluation of first and second step formation constants (K_1 and K_2 respectively) of binary complexes in M-L systems under identical conditions has enabled a comparison with the corresponding values of ternary complexes ($K_{M.bipy.L}^M$)

Experimental

Solutions were prepared in double distilled CO₂ free water and all the chemicals were of AnalaR grade. Aqueous solutions of metal nitrates, nitric acid and potassium hydroxide were prepared and used after standardization³. Aqueous solutions of KNO₃, bipy and ethanolic solutions of 1, 2 HNA and 2, 1 HNA were prepared by direct weighing. pH-measurements were made using a Philips pH-meter (PR 9405M) with a glass-calomel electrode assembly at a constant temperature of 25° ± 0.1, in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen, and at an ionic strength 0.1 (KNO₃).

Procedure :

The following titration mixtures were prepared in each case and titrated individually against standard KOH solution (N° = 0.1042M) : (A) HNO₃ + KNO₃, (B) mixture A+L, (C) mixture B+metal ion, (D) mixture A+bipy, (E) mixture D+metal ion, and (F) mixture E+L. The total volume was kept 50 ml ; the proportion of water and ethanol being adjusted to 50% v/v aqueous-ethanol media. In each case ionic strength was maintained by KNO₃ solution. The final concentrations in the binary systems were : $E^\circ = 0.002M$, $TC_L^\circ = 0.001M$ and $TC_M^\circ = 0.0002M$, while in the ternary systems these were : TC_{bipy}° (total initial concentration of bipy) = $TC_M^\circ = TC_L^\circ = 0.001M$; the concentrations of other components being the same as in the binary

systems. All the symbols used have their usual meanings¹.

Results and Discussion

The parameters $\bar{n}A$, \bar{n} and pL were evaluated to determine the protonation constants of the ligands and the formation constants of the binary complexes in M-L systems (Table 1). In M-L systems when L=1,2-HNA, the \bar{n} values extend over ≈ 0-1.8 in case of Cu(II) and Co(II) ions, but these do not exceed even unity with Ni(II) ion. Hence, Cu(II) and Co(II) form both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes, but Ni(II) forms only 1 : 1. In case of L=2,1 HNA, while Cu(II) ions form both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complex species, Ni(II) and Co(II) form only 1 : 1. The stabilities of the metal complexes follow the trend : Cu(II) > Ni(II) > Co(II), which conforms to the Irving William's order. The stability order with respect to the ligands is 1,2 HNA > 2,1 HNA. In Ni(II) complexes, however, the values are identical within experimental error.

In M-bipy-L systems complete formation of (M.bipy)²⁺ species occurs at pH ≤ 4.0 and remain stable at pH ≈ 6.0, 7.8 and 7.9 respectively in the cases of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) and thereafter the formation of hydroxo complexes appears likely. Subsequently precipitation takes place at pH ≈ 10.7, 8.7 and 8.3 for Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) respectively. Thus, the average number of secondary ligand molecules attached per (M.bipy)²⁺ ion (\bar{n}_{mix}) and free ligand exponent (pL_{mix}) were evaluated as described earlier⁴⁻⁸, whereby the formation constants of ternary complexes were evaluated (Table 1).

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BINARY AND TERNARY METAL CHELATES (25°, $\mu=0.1$)

Reactions	$L-1,2\ HNA$	log (equil. const.)
$L^{2-} + H^+ \rightleftharpoons LH^-$		11.76 ± 0.03
$LH^- + H^+ \rightleftharpoons LH_2^0$		3.87 ± 0.03
$Cu^{2+} + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons CuL^0$		9.36 ± 0.02
$CuL^0 + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons CuL_2^{2-}$		7.01 ± 0.02
$Ni^{2+} + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons NiL^0$		6.99 ± 0.02
$NiL^0 + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons NiL_2^{2-}$...
$Co^{2+} + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons CoL^0$		6.86 ± 0.02
$CoL^0 + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons CoL_2^{2-}$		5.38 ± 0.02
$(Cu.bipy)^{2+} + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons (Cu.bipy.L)^0$		9.96 ± 0.02
$(Ni.bipy)^{2+} + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons (Ni.bipy.L)^0$		6.76 ± 0.02
$(Co.bipy)^{2+} + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons (Co.bipy.L)^0$		6.65 ± 0.02
	$L-2,1\ HNA$	
$L^{2-} + H^+ \rightleftharpoons LH^-$		11.98 ± 0.01
$LH^- + H^+ \rightleftharpoons LH_2^0$		3.94 ± 0.03
$Cu^{2+} + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons CuL^0$		8.68 ± 0.02
$CuL^0 + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons CuL_2^{2-}$		6.17 ± 0.01
$Ni^{2+} + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons NiL^0$		6.96 ± 0.02
$NiL^0 + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons NiL_2^{2-}$...
$Co^{2+} + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons CoL^0$		6.77 ± 0.01
$CoL^0 + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons CoL_2^{2-}$...
$(Cu.bipy)^{2+} + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons (Cu.bipy.L)^0$		8.98 ± 0.02
$(Ni.bipy)^{2+} + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons (Ni.bipy.L)^0$		6.86 ± 0.02
$(Co.bipy)^{2+} + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons (Co.bipy.L)^0$		6.20 ± 0.03

* To whom all correspondence may be addressed.

Various factors affecting stability, structure and reactivity of ternary complexes in solution have been extensively dealt by Sigel⁹. From statistical considerations $\log K_{M. \text{bipy}}^M$ is expected to be appreciably less than $\log K_1$, as the concentration of electrons around the metal ion in $(M. \text{bipy})^{2+}$ is more than in $[M(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]^{2+}$ owing to greater coordinating tendency of bipy than that of water.

However, $\log K_1 \approx \log K_{M. \text{bipy}}^M$. This anomaly could perhaps be best explained in terms of indirect interactions (ternary complexes in which the two kinds of ligands 'simply' coordinate to the same metal ion), particularly by way of formation of π bonds⁹. There appears to be $M-N\pi$ interaction on account of back donation of the electrons from metal $d\pi$ -orbital to the vacant delocalized π -orbital over the bipy molecule, in addition to the σ -bond between the two nitrogen atoms of the bipy molecule. Thus, the concentration of electrons around the metal ion in $(M. \text{bipy})^{2+}$ does not increase significantly as a result of which electronegativity of the metal ion in this species remains almost the same as in $[M(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]^{2+}$, which justifies $\log K_1 \approx \log K_{M. \text{bipy}}^M$. On the other hand,

$\log K_{M. \text{bipy}}^M > \log K_2$, may be explained on the basis that during the formation of ML_2 species there is a coulombic repulsion between the negative oxygens of the two ligand anions tending to lower the stability of ML_2 specie, there is no such repulsion in the case of ternary complexes.

A plot of $\log K_{M. \text{bipy}}^M$ versus $\log K_1$ is linear indicating that the process of association of L with $(M. \text{bipy})^{2+}$ species in the ternary system, follows the same pattern as that of the association of L^{2-} with $[M(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]^{2+}$ in the corresponding binary system.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (PKD) is thankful to the Principal, D.H.S.K. College, Dibrugarh, Assam for providing necessary facilities and for the grant of study leave towards the completion of this work.

References

1. M. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3997. 1964, 2904.
2. M. V. CHIDAMBARAM and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 3271; *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **9**, 1294.
3. M. A. FLASCHKA, EDTA Titrations (Pergamon, New York), 1964, p. 82.
4. K. DWIVEDI, M. CHANDRA and A. K. DEY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, **14A**, 900, *Trans. Metal Chem.*, 1977, **2**, 186.
5. K. DWIVEDI, B. K. AGRAWAL, M. CHANDRA and A. K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 474.

6. B. K. AGRAWAL, M. CHANDRA, B. V. AGARWALA and A. K. DEY, *Trans. Metal Chem.*, 1978, **3**, 249.
7. R. K. MITTAL, M. CHANDRA and A. K. DEY, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1978, **109**, 853, 953.
8. P. K. DATTA, M. CHANDRA and A. K. DEY, *Trans. Metal Chem.* 1980, **5**, 1.
9. H. SIGEL, Plenary Lecture, XXth Int. Conf. Coord. Chem., Calcutta, Dec. 1979, Pergamon Press, Oxford (under publication) and the references cited therein.

A Nickel(II) Complex of a New Hydrazone Type Macrocyclic Ligand

R. L. DUTTA* and A. K. SARKAR

Department of Chemistry, The University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713 104, West Bengal, India

Manuscript received 30 November 1979, accepted 9 July 1980

SINCE Melson and Busch¹ reported the efficacy of a metal ion, particularly nickel(II), indicating the synthesis of a macrocyclic ligand through self-condensation of *o*-amino benzaldehyde, a large number of reports have appeared in the literature concerning synthesis of metal chelates of a variety of macrocyclic ligand²⁻⁸. These macrocyclic ligands have all nitrogen⁴, all sulphur⁵, all oxygen⁶, or nitrogen-sulphur⁷ or nitrogen-oxygen as donor centres⁸. We wish to report here a nickel complex of a new macrocyclic ligand(III) prepared by the reaction of *bis*(acetyl acetone) ethylene diimine(II) with carbonylhydrazide(I) in presence of nickel(II) ion.

Experimental

Materials and Methods:

A. Synthesis of the ligands :

(i) *Ethyl ester of carbazic acid* : $\text{H}_2\text{N}-\text{NH}-\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$

Its synthesis and properties have already been described in an earlier paper from this laboratory⁹.

(ii) *Preparation of carbonylhydrazide* : $\text{NH}_2-\text{NH}-\text{CO}-\text{NH}-\text{NH}_2$

This has been described earlier^{9,10}.

(iii) *Preparation of bis(acetylacetone) ethylene diimine* :

This Schiff base was prepared following standard procedure¹¹. (m.p. 111°; lit., m.p. 111.5°).

B. Synthesis of the complex :

(i) *Preparation of tetraphenyl boron salt of the nickel(II) macrocyclic complex.*

Nickel(II) chloride hexahydrate (.005 mole, dissolved in 2 ml rectified spirit) was added to a hot